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EFFECT OF SPIRULINA ON THE ANOMALIES CAUSED BY MALATHION IN FRESHWATER PRAWN *MACROBRACHIUM LAMARREI LAMARREI*

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ABSTRACT

Commercially high stocking density of culture practice, the feeding has the significant contribution for fast growth and high yields. The aqua feed is potentiated with many ingredients in highly balanced nutritious components for enhancing the digestive mechanisms in fish and shrimp body. Spirulina has been shown to enhance immune function, reproduction, increase growth and good health. The present investigation has been conducted to understand the effect of spirulina as a feed supplement on health and survival of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* for a period of 90 days. Highest values for health and survival gain in the prawns were observed in prawns fed with 5% Spirulina feed which was recorded to be 94% in case of survival rate and good health. Hence coming to conclusion that using Spirulina in the prawns can improve its health and survival ability.

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INTRODUCTION

Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei (H. Milne Edwards), the freshwater prawn belong to the category of minor prawns is widely distributed in waterbodies of Bhopal. The target species in terms of availability and size compete well with other exploitable species of smaller prawn and thus constitute an important local food resource. Proteins are important organic substances required in tissue building and repair under extreme stress conditions, protein supplies' energy in metabolic pathways and biochemical reactions (Vishwaranjan et al., 1988).

Spirulina platensis, the blue-green algae has been used as a food source for humans and animals from hundreds of years due to excellent nutritional profile and high carotenoid content. Spirulina is relatively high in protein with values ranging from 55-65% and include all of the essential amino acids (Clement et al., 1967; Bourges et al., 1971 and Anusuya et al., 1981). The available energy has been determined to be 2.5-3.29 kcal/gram and phosphorous availability is 41% (Yoshida and Hoshii, 1980 and Blum et al., 1976). Spirulina algae is rich in thiamin, riboflavin, pyridoxine, vitamin B12, vitamin C and antioxidant carotenoids and has been used throughout the world as a feed component (Blum et al., 1976; Colas et al., 1979; Brune, 1982; Ross and Dominy, 1985).

Pesticides are the chemicals or any agents to kill or control pests or undesired organisms like insects, weeds, rodents, fungi and bacteria. (USEPA, 2007) but the contamination of fresh water with a wide range of pesticides has become a matter of concern over the few decades (Dirilgen 2001, Voegborlo et al., 1999 and Canli et al., 1998).

Keeping in view the health hazards caused by organophosphate pesticide, malathion to prawns, Spirulina was tested as a health food to overcome the anomalies caused due to toxicity caused by malathion to them by observing the changes altered in protein concentration along with survival rate of prawns when exposed to malathion and fed with Spirulina.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection and Acclimation of Experimental Prawn *Macrobrachium lamarrei* (H. Milne-Edward, 1837):

Macrobrachium lamarrei (H. Milne-Edward, 1837) with average length of 3-4 cm were procured from Upper Lake, Bhopal, M.P, India. The prawns were brought to laboratory of Department of Zoology & Applied Aquaculture, Barkatullah University and were kept in the glass aquarium to observe visible pathological symptoms. The prawns were then treated with 0.1 KMnO₄ solutions to obviate any dermal infection before introducing them into the aquaria; the prawns were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for two weeks prior to exposure to Malathion. During this period, the prawns were fed 4% of their body weight once daily with laboratory formulated feed (Table 1). Each aquarium was supplied with dechlorinated, well-aerated tap water, an aerator and holed PVC pipes for hiding as the prawns are nocturnal. Water was changed after every third day. After the acclimatization period, the prawns were randomly selected and stocked at the rate of 40 prawns per aquarium in two glass aquaria for the experimental runs.

Preparation of Malathion solution:

Malathion in original package form, by mixing with distilled water was used as stock-solution by adopting the dilution techniques (APHA, 1985). Different test doses were prepared making dilution of the stock concentration.

Determination of LC₅₀:

Prawns were transferred to each aquarium and were exposed to different concentrations of Malathion. In all cases, control groups of prawns were maintained. Each experimental trial was carried out for a period of 96 hours. 10 prawns were exposed to sub-lethal concentration for each trial. The mortality of the prawns was recorded at logarithmic time intervals that is, after 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours of exposure. The test media was renewed daily during the experimental period. The effect of each concentration was tested at least in duplicate to verify reproducibility. The data obtained in course of the investigation was analyzed statistically to see whether there is any influence of different treatments (concentrations) on the mortality of prawn. The median lethal concentration (LC₅₀) values and their 95% confidence limits for different exposure time were calculated by using the computer software "Probit Analysis", EPA version 1.5, USA. The LC₅₀ value came out to be 10 ppm.

Dose of Malathion used in experiment:

The experiment was set for 90 days in aquaria of 200 L capacity. Each group contained 30 prawns of almost same size and length. Group first was kept as unexposed control; IInd Group was exposed to sub lethal concentrations of 1 ppm malathion whereas group IIIrd was also exposed to Malathion and fed with 5% Spirulina.

Preparation of Normal and Spirulina Supplemented Feed

Normal feed was prepared by taking fish meal (55%), wheat flour (40%) and Cod liver oil (5%) whereas Spirulina supplemented feed was prepared by taking fish meal (50%), wheat flour (40%), Cod liver oil (5%) and Spirulina (5%). Spirulina was replaced with fishmeal due to its closest range of protein level.

Ingredients of normal feed were ground finely, mixed together with required quantity of water and thus the dough was prepared. The dough, thus prepared was passed through extrudes, dried in hot air oven at 60 - 70⁰C temperature and broken in pieces of desirable size. Same procedure was applied in preparation of Spirulina supplemented feed. Experimental prawns were fed with these feeds once daily @ 10% of their body weight and the residue if any was removed immediately after the maximum feed was consumed.

Table 1. Composition of Normal and *Spirulina* supplemented feed.

Ingredients	% Dry weight (Normal feed)	% Dry weight (<i>Spirulina</i> supplemented feed)
Fish meal	55%	50%
Wheat flour	40%	40%
Cod liver oil	5%	5%
<i>Spirulina</i>	-	5%
Total	100%	100%

BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Protein Estimation

Protein concentration in hepatopancreas of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* in Controlled group; exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with normal feed as well as Prawns exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina* was estimated after every 30 days for a period of 90 days by following Lowry method (Lowry et al., 1951)

Procedure:

0.2 ml of BSA working standard in 5 test tubes was made up to 1ml using distilled water. The test tube with 1 ml distilled water served as blank. 4.5 ml of 2% Na_2CO_3 in 0.1 N NaOH was added and incubated for 10 minutes. After incubation 0.5 ml of 1% NaK tartrate in H_2O reagent was added and incubated for 30 minutes. The absorbance was measured at 660 nm and the standard graph was plotted and finally the amount of protein present in the given sample from the standard graph was estimated. Standard was prepared by mixing 0.2 ml of standard cholesterol and 5 ml of phosphovanillin reagent by allowing it to stand for half an hour. Blank was prepared by taking 0.2 ml of chloroform and 5 ml of phosphovanili reagent. Test and standard was read against the blank at 520nm.

Survival rate

Survival rate was observed in *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* of Controlled group; exposed to 1 ppm Malathion and fed with normal feed as well as Prawns exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina* was estimated after termination of 90 days experiment

RESULTS

Protein concentration in hepatopancreas of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* in Controlled group; exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with normal feed as well as Prawns exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina*.

As regard to protein content in hepatopancreas of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* of controlled group for the period of 30, 60 and 90 days, the values observed were 70.24, 68.20 and 67.85 mg/g respectively.

In the prawns, exposed to 1 ppm malathion alone for the period of 30, 60 and 90 days, the values of protein in hepatopancreas have been observed as 56.15, 40.17 and 32.19 mg/g respectively.

In the prawns, exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina* for the period of 30, 60 and 90 days, the values of protein in hepatopancreas have been observed as 64.42, 57.50 and 49.62 mg/g respectively.

Table 2. Showing the protein concentration in hepatopancreas of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* in control group; exposed to 0.1 ppm malathion alone; exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina* for different time periods.

Days of Exposure	Protein concentration in hepatopancreas of <i>M. lamarrei lamarrei</i> of Control group (mg/g)	Protein concentration in hepatopancreas of <i>M. lamarrei lamarrei</i> exposed to 1 ppm malathion alone (mg/g)	Protein concentration in hepatopancreas of <i>M. lamarrei lamarrei</i> exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% <i>Spirulina</i> (mg/g)
30 days	70.24	56.15	64.42
60 days	68.20	40.17	57.50
90 days	67.85	32.19	49.62

Survival rate of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* in Controlled group; exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with normal feed as well as Prawns exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina*.

Survival rate in *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* of controlled group after 90 days experiment was 86.6%.

Survival rate in *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* exposed to 1 ppm malathion alone after the period 90 days came out to be 66.6%.

Survival rate in *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% *Spirulina* after the period of 90 days was 80%.

Table 3. Showing the survival rate of *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei* in control group; exposed to 0.1 ppm malathion alone; exposed to 0.1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% Spirulina at the termination of experiment.

Survival Rate of <i>M. lamarrei lamarrei</i> of Control group (%)	Survival Rate of <i>M. lamarrei lamarrei</i> exposed to 1 ppm malathion alone (%)	Survival Rate of <i>M. lamarrei lamarrei</i> exposed to 1 ppm malathion and fed with 5% Spirulina (%)
86.6	66.6	80

DISCUSSION

In the present study it was observed that, when prawns *M. lamarrei lamarrei* were exposed to sub lethal concentration of 1ppm malathion for 90 days, protein content in hepatopancreas decreased drastically with the increase in duration of malathion but when treated with Spirulina showed improvement. Same was the condition in case of survival rate.

Similar results were also observed by Desai and Tank (2008). In their study fresh water prawns, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* showed drastic reduction in protein content of muscle tissue. Proteins are building blocks of animal tissues and in general prawn muscles are consumed as delicacy by human (Desai et al., (2008). Malathion is not only neurotoxic but also affects other systems and has shown a high degree of impact on metabolism by altering the carbohydrates, proteins and lipid levels (Mckee et al., 1986 and Nagabhushanam et al., 1972). Reddy and Rao (1991) also found a decrease in the protein level in the marine prawn *Metapenaeus monoceros* after the prawn was exposed to the pesticide methyl parathion. Geraldine et al., 1999 reported protein depletion in the freshwater prawn *Macrobrachium malcolmsonii* in response to dichlorovos exposure. Marked decrease in protein content in the freshwater field crab *Pratelphusa hydrodromous* in response to the pesticide Malathion toxicity (Singaraju et al., 1991) has been reported.

The study of using Spirulina platensis in different dry weights for nursing black tiger shrimp post larvae 10 showed that the growth of shrimp larvae fed by using 5% of Spirulina platensis was significantly higher (14.25mm) than that of shrimp larvae in control and the survival rates for treatment groups were also higher (69.5%) than that of control (Hemtanon et al., 2008).

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